

Synthesis and sintering of nanocrystalline Ce³⁺ - doped yttria nanoparticles prepared by precipitation method

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Cubic yttria is widely known as a promising optical material owing to its broad range transparency, outstanding refractoriness, and excellent chemical stability. Using nanoparticle as starting material is found to be potential to fabricate ceramics not only achieving transparency but also considerably diminish sintering temperature [1, 2].

Cerium doped yttrium oxide (Y_{1.999}Ce_{0.001}O₃, Y_{1.995}Ce_{0.005}O₃, Y_{1.99}Ce_{0.01}O₃) nanoparticles have been synthesized by precipitation method. The vacuum - pressure filtration was performed in a special die with a diameter of 15 mm. The suspension (30 vol % solid loading) was poured into the die and after losing the mould, a pressure of 20 bars was applied by a hydraulic press. The water from the suspension was drained through massive perforated metal bottom with a polymeric membrane (pore size 0.2 μm). The green body was air-calcined at 900 °C to remove the organic and then sintered at 1550 °C for 3 hrs at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The samples were hot isostatic pressing (HIP) at 1500 °C for 1 h under an Ar gas pressure of 180 MPa. Relative density of sintered samples was determined by Archimedes principle in water.

Figure 1 shows the EBSD image of polished ceria doped yttria ceramics prepared by vacuum pressure filtration, sintered at 1550 °C for 3 hrs. The samples are coarse-crystalline with compact grain structure, sintered to high density, with closed porosity. The grain boundaries were sharply defined and grains are in range 2-6 μm. Ceria doping did not show any influence on the microstructure of the sintered ceramics.

Fig. 1: The EBSD image of sintered samples and particle size distribution Ce³⁺ doped Y₂O₃ ceramics, Ce-1) 0.001 mol % Ce³⁺, Ce-2) 0.005 mol % Ce³⁺, Ce-3) 0.01 mol % Ce³⁺.

Figure 2 shows the image of polished ceria doped yttria ceramics after applying the hot isostatic press (HIP, 1500 °C for 1 h). The samples show an orange-reddish colour which is due to the doping of the samples with Ce³⁺. Consequently, doping of sample with 0.001 mol % Ce³⁺ resulted in light orange colour, while increasing of the dopant concentration leads to the darker orange-reddish colour. It is caused by the presence of oxygen vacancies resulted from the reducing conditions in the HIP, which give rise to the formation of F and F⁺ centers in the wide band gap [3, 4].

Fig. 2: Photography of ceria doped yttria ceramics hot isostatic pressing (HIP) at 1500 °C for 1 h, Ce-1) 0.001 mol % Ce³⁺, Ce-2) 0.005 mol % Ce³⁺ Ce-3) 0.01 mol % Ce³⁺.

The relative density of Ce³⁺ doped yttria ceramics before and after HIP is summarized in Table 1. Generally, increasing of the dopant concentration leads to the higher densities after sintering. This is more obvious before applying HIP, where the difference in density between 0,001 Ce³⁺ and 0, 01 Ce³⁺ is almost 0.7 %.

Table 1: Relative density of Ce³⁺ doped yttria ceramic.

Sample	Relative density	
	1550 °C /3h	HIP 1500°C /1h
0.001 Ce ³⁺	97.88 %	99.75%
0.005 Ce ³⁺	98.38 %	99.79%
0.010 Ce ³⁺	98.57 %	99.89%

Keywords: Ceramic, EBSD, HIP, Precipitation, Y₂O₃.

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